

Kinetics and Mechanism of Reduction of Rhenium(V) by Sn(II) in Hydrochloric Acid Media

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Spectrophotometric studies on the kinetics of reduction of rhenium(V) by Sn(II) in hydrochloric acid media have shown that the rate is of first order with respect to both rhenium(V) and the acid, 0.5 order with respect to Sn(II), and is independent of Sn(IV). A possible mechanism has been suggested assuming that under the experimental conditions Sn(II) is present in solution in a binuclear form. The activation energy of the process is 12.8 kcal. per mole.

Rhenium is known to exhibit all the oxidation states from -1 to 7. Earlier potentiometric and spectrophotometric studies¹ have shown that rhenium(VII) in the form of perrhenate ion, ReO_4^- , is reduced by Sn(II) in hydrochloric acid medium to rhenium(V) and then slowly to rhenium(IV). Results of investigations on the kinetics of the second step form the subject matter of this communication. The change has been followed spectrophotometrically.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the chemicals used were of the purest quality. A stock solution of potassium perrhenate was prepared by dissolving a requisite quantity of the recrystallised pure salt in distilled water. A solution of stannous chloride was prepared in HCl (dil.) and stored in an atmosphere of hydrogen. This was standardised against potassium iodate as usual. A stock solution of stannic chloride was prepared by oxidising the stannous chloride solution with hydrogen peroxide and boiling.

Distilled water, redistilled in an all-glass apparatus with alkaline permanganate, was used for making the solutions.

The spectrophotometric measurements were carried out with a Hilger Uvispek spectrophotometer having a thermostatic cell carriage. Stoppered cells (2 cm) of fused quartz were used. In the solutions for kinetic studies, the concentration of HCl was maintained at 3M or more in order to prevent precipitation of rhenium(IV) oxide. In all the experiments, the concentration of Sn(II) was at least ten times the concentration of rhenium(V) formed *in situ* by the reduction of rhenium(VII), ReO_4^- , with excess of Sn(II). Under the experimental conditions, the reduction of rhenium(VII) to rhenium(V) was almost instantaneous and hence the increase in optical density, observed at 550 m μ , was due to further reduction of rhenium(V) to rhenium(IV).

Absorbance measurements were made at 550 m μ because in this region the difference in the extinction coefficients of the rhenium species involved in the reaction is known¹ to be large, whereas the tin species have no absorbance. The pseudo first-order rate constants were evaluated graphically by the method of Guggenheim².

TABLE I

Re(V) = 0.003*M*. Temp. = 35.5° ± 0.1°.

Effect of Sn(II). HCl = 4 <i>M</i> .		Effect of HCl.	Sn(II) = 0.03 <i>M</i> .
Sn(II).	$k_{obs} \times 10^2$ (min ⁻¹).	HCl.	$k_{obs} \times 10^2$ (min ⁻¹).
0.03 <i>M</i>	5.75, 6.19	3.0 <i>M</i>	4.9, 5.24
0.03			
[with Sn(IV), 0.03 <i>M</i>]	5.84	3.5	5.6
0.035	6.56, 6.99	4.0	5.75, 6.19
0.045	7.2	4.5	6.51
0.055	8.17	5.0	7.02
0.060	8.52, 8.9	6.0	8.42

DISCUSSION

The pseudo first-order rate constants (k_{obs}), evaluated under different conditions at 35.5°, are recorded in Table I. The results indicate that the rate is dependent on the concentration of Sn(II) and HCl, but is independent of Sn(IV). The order with respect to each of the two species, namely Sn(II) and HCl, was evaluated by plotting the logarithm of the observed pseudo first-order rate constant against the logarithm of the concentration of a species at a fixed concentration of the other. The slope of the straight line, thus obtained, is the order of the reaction with respect to that particular species. Values of 0.5 and 0.9 were thus obtained for Sn(II) and HCl respectively. The latter value is believed to indicate an order of unity with respect to the acid. Hence the rate law for the reaction can be expressed as

$$\text{Rate} = k(\text{Re}) (\text{Sn}^{II})^{0.5} (\text{HCl}).$$

It should, however, be pointed out in this connection that although the effect of Sn(II) on the rate of the reaction was investigated at nearly constant ionic strength, this was not possible for experiments on the effect of HCl.

Under the experimental conditions, rhenium(V) is most likely³ to exist in solution as ReOCl_2^{2-} and rhenium(IV) as $\text{Re}(\text{OH})\text{Cl}_3^{2-}$. In HCl medium, Sn(II) is known to exist as chloro complexes. A complex acid of the formula $\text{HSnCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ has been isolated and salts of the types $\text{M}(\text{I})\text{SnCl}_3$ and $\text{M}(\text{II})\text{SnCl}_4$ are known³. The rate expression, stated above, can be arrived at by assuming that in solution Sn(II) is present essentially in the

2. Phil. Mag., 1926, vii, 2, 538.

3. Remy, "Treatise on Inorganic Chemistry", Vol. I, p. 535, Elsevier Publishing Co., 1956.

binuclear form, $H_2Sn_2Cl_6$, which is in equilibrium with $HSnCl_3$ and H_2SnCl_4 , the actual concentration of the latter being negligible.

where K_1 and K_2 are the equilibrium constants. The following is the mechanism by which rhenium(V) is believed to be reduced to rhenium(IV):

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Rate} &= -d(1)/dt = d(3)/dt = k_1(1)(2) + k_2(1)(4); \text{ and} \\ d(4)/dt &= k_1(1)(2) - k_2(1)(4) = 0 \text{ (assuming } k_2 \gg k_1). \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$\text{Rate} = 2k_1(1)(2) = 2k_1(Re^V)(H_2SnCl_4).$$

Considering the equilibria in the tin (II) solution in hydrochloric acid, it can be shown that

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Rate} &= 2^{0.5} k_1 K_1^{0.5} K_2 (Re^V) (Sn^{II})^{0.5} (HCl) \\ &= k(Re^V) (Sn^{II})^{0.5} (HCl), \end{aligned}$$

where (Sn^{II}) stands for the analytical concentration of Sn(II) in solution. When Sn(II) and hydrochloric acid are in excess, the above equation reduces to

$$\text{Rate} = k_{obs} (Re^V).$$

The activation energy of the process has been determined graphically in the usual way from the Arrhenius relation, using the data recorded in Table II. A value of 12.8 kcal. per mole has been obtained.

TABLE II

$$Re(V) = 0.003M. \quad Sn(II) = 0.03M. \quad HCl = 3M.$$

Temp.	30°	35°	40°
$k_{obs} \times 10^2 \text{ (min}^{-1}\text{)}$	3.73	4.9, 5.24	7.68

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